

Patterns of Integer Solutions to Non-homogeneous Ternary Heptic Diophantine Equation

$$x^2 + y^2 = (a^2 + b^2)z^7$$

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Abstract

This paper aims at determining non-zero distinct integer solutions to non-homogeneous ternary heptic Diophantine equation $x^2 + y^2 = (a^2 + b^2)z^7$. Transformation techniques and factorization methods are utilized to obtain the same.

Keywords: Ternary heptic equation, Non-homogeneous heptic equation, Integer solutions, Transformation technique, Factorization method

Introduction

The theory of Diophantine equations is an ancient subject that typically involves solving, polynomial equation in two or more variables or a system of polynomial equations with the number of unknowns greater than the number of equations, in integers and occupies a pivotal role in the region of mathematics. The subject of Diophantine equations has fascinated and

inspired both amateurs and mathematicians alike and so they merit special recognition. Solving higher degree Diophantine equations can be challenging as they involve finding integer solutions that satisfy the given polynomial equation. Various techniques to solve these higher power Diophantine equation in successfully deriving their solutions help us understand how numbers work and their significance in different areas of mathematics and science. For the sake of clear understanding by the readers, one may refer the varieties of Cubic, Quintic, Sextic and Heptic Diophantine equations with multi variables [1-37]. This paper aims at determining many integer solutions to non-homogeneous polynomial equation of degree seven with three unknowns given by $x^2 + y^2 = (a^2 + b^2)z^7$.

Method of analysis

The non-homogeneous ternary heptic Diophantine equation to be solved is

$$x^2 + y^2 = (a^2 + b^2)z^7 \quad (1)$$

To start with, it is seen that (1) is satisfied by

$$x = a\alpha^7, y = b\alpha^7, z = \alpha^2$$

The process of obtaining other patterns of integer solutions to (1) is illustrated below:

Pattern 1

The insertion of the linear transformations

$$x = (a^2 + b^2)^4 \alpha^3, z = (a^2 + b^2)\alpha \quad (2)$$

in (1) leads to the equation

$$y^2 = (a^2 + b^2)^8 \alpha^6 (\alpha - 1) \quad (3)$$

Taking

$$\alpha = s^2 + 1 \quad (4)$$

in the above equation (3), one obtains

$$y = (a^2 + b^2)^4 (s^2 + 1)^3 s \quad (5)$$

Substituting (4) in (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (a^2 + b^2)^4 (s^2 + 1)^3 \\ z &= (a^2 + b^2)(s^2 + 1) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Thus, (5) & (6) satisfy (1).

Pattern 2

The choice

$$y = a z^3 \quad (7)$$

in (1) gives

$$x^2 = z^6 [(a^2 + b^2)z - a^2] \quad (8)$$

Let

$$\alpha^2 = (a^2 + b^2)z - a^2 \quad (9)$$

which is satisfied by

$$z = z_0 = 1, \alpha = \alpha_0 = b$$

Assume the second solution to (9) as

$$z_1 = h + z_0, \alpha_1 = h - \alpha_0 \quad (10)$$

where h is an unknown to be determined. Substituting (10) in (9) and simplifying, we get

$$h = 2\alpha_0 + (a^2 + b^2)$$

From (10), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= \alpha_0 + (a^2 + b^2) \\ z_1 &= z_0 + 2\alpha_0 + (a^2 + b^2) \end{aligned}$$

The repetition of the above process leads to the general solution to (9) as

$$\begin{aligned} z_n &= z_0 + 2n\alpha_0 + (a^2 + b^2)n^2 = 1 + 2nb + (a^2 + b^2)n^2 \\ \alpha_n &= \alpha_0 + (a^2 + b^2)n = b + (a^2 + b^2)n \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

From (7) & (8), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} y_n &= a[1 + 2nb + (a^2 + b^2)n^2]^3 \\ x_n &= [1 + 2nb + (a^2 + b^2)n^2]^3 [b + (a^2 + b^2)n] \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z given by (11) & (12) satisfy (1).

Pattern 3

Let us assume

$$z = r^2 + s^2 \tag{13}$$

Substitute (13) in (1). Employing the factorization and equating the positive factors, consider

$$\begin{aligned} x + iy &= (a + ib)(r + is)^7 \\ &= (a + ib)[f(r,s) + ig(r,s)] \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f(r,s) &= r^7 - 21r^5s^2 + 35r^3s^4 - 7rs^6 \\ g(r,s) &= 7r^6s - 35r^4s^3 + 21r^2s^5 - s^7 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

On equating the real and imaginary parts in (14), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &= af(r,s) - bg(r,s) \\ y &= bf(r,s) + ag(r,s) \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Thus, (13) & (16) satisfy (1).

Pattern 4

Rewrite (1) as

$$x^2 + y^2 = (a^2 + b^2) z^7 * 1 \tag{17}$$

Assume the integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (17) as

$$1 = \frac{(F(p,q) + iG(p,q))(F(p,q) - iG(p,q))}{(H(p,q))^2} \tag{18}$$

where

$$F(p,q) = p^2 - q^2, G(p,q) = 2pq, H(p,q) = p^2 + q^2$$

Substitute (13), (18) in (17). Employing the method of factorization and equating the positive factors, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (x + iy) &= (a + ib)(f(r,s) + ig(r,s)) \frac{(F(p,q) + iG(p,q))}{H(p,q)} \\ &= \{[af(r,s) - bg(r,s)] + i[b f(r,s) + a g(r,s)]\} \frac{(F(p,q) + iG(p,q))}{H(p,q)} \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

On comparing the coefficients of corresponding terms in (19), one has

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{[af(r,s) - bg(r,s)]F(p,q) - [b f(r,s) + a g(r,s)]G(p,q)}{H(p,q)} \\ y &= \frac{[af(r,s) - bg(r,s)]G(p,q) + [b f(r,s) + a g(r,s)]F(p,q)}{H(p,q)} \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

As our aim is to obtain integer solutions, replacing r by $H(p,q)R$ and s by $H(p,q)S$ in (13)

and (20), we have

$$z = (H(p,q))^2 (R^2 + S^2) \tag{21}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (H(p,q))^6 [af(r,s) - bg(r,s)]F(p,q) - [b f(r,s) + a g(r,s)]G(p,q) \\ y &= (H(p,q))^6 [af(r,s) - bg(r,s)]G(p,q) + [b f(r,s) + a g(r,s)]F(p,q) \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Thus, (21) & (22) satisfy (1).

Conclusion

Solving the higher degree Diophantine equation and finding the non-zero distinct integer solutions are used in various fields like cryptography, Number patterns. The concepts of Diophantine equations are encouraging the young researchers to discover new ideas in various fields like some mentioned above. To conclude, one may search for different types of higher degree Diophantine equations and their solutions.

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